

Workshop
FAIR Metrics in Engineering Sciences

Modellierung, Tribina Hristova, A. Kaya-Abdulkay, Robert G. Schwarz
 Center for Data Science and Engineering, Department of Mechanical, Aerospace and Astronautics, Faculty of Aeronautics, Istanbul Technical University, Istanbul, Turkey
 rtschwarz@itu.edu.tr

Workshop Conference 2023
 Track 23: JForum for FAIR FAIR play a improved rules for the case?
 27 September 2023, 12:30 - 1:45, online

Contributors of today's workshop, that would like to be named (open a PDF file in a publication about this workshop)

What is 'highlighting' for you - which digital objects do you work with?

Setting - to which area might each a metric apply?

Any feedback? Feel free to give it here - thank you!

